

Resource Allocation using Fog-IoT NOMA Technique for 5G Long-Range Communication

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Abstract— The incoming 5G technology is expected to proliferate tremendous internet-of-thing (IoT) services with real-time and mobility requirements, which are quite different from the legacy cloud services. This research presents Fog-IoT-based Long-Range (LoRa) Communication for 5G applications. Research is done based on optimally provision the huge volume of IoT services with significant diversity, efficiently organize the leisure network devices in the network edge to form fog networks (fogs), which are then integrated with the cloud to provide storage and computing resources for 5G applications.

Keywords— Fog-Node, NOMA, Hybrid, Power Allocation, Resource block, LORA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional Next-generation 5G access systems are being investigated as an answer for the dangerous increment in remote data traffic figure for the 2020s and the quick appearance of different new [1]. Three methodologies are being taken towards supporting this immense traffic expands: utilizing accessible frequencies, expanding network speeds, and opening-up new frequency bands [2]. Utilizing accessible frequencies is firmly related to accelerating the physical layer for multi-access and remote access advances. For instance, increments of from 2.5 to multiple times have been proposed as focuses for expanding the proficiency of 5G frequencies [3].

The iCloudFog framework consists of three layers, i.e., IoT end layer, fog layer and cloud layer from bottom to top. The bottom IoT layer consists of various types IoT devices, such as sensors, smartphones, wearable devices, tablets, etc [4]. These tremendous IoT devices generate a large volume of heavyweight or lightweight IoT tasks that would require services from fogs and/or cloud. Note that we assume there is no direct connection from the IoT end layer to the cloud. Any IoT task must bypass some wired fog node in the fog layer to access the resources in the cloud, if needed [5].

The middle fog layer is mainly composed of wireless and wired fog nodes, which can provide network resources such as transmission bandwidth and computing/storage resources [6]. In this layer, we dynamically organize the candidate fog nodes

to form different fog types, i.e., wireless fogs (WLF), wired fogs (WDF), and hybrid fogs (HBF) as shown in Fig 1, with the objective of optimally satisfying diverse QoS requirements of the uploaded IoT tasks while minimizing the required cloud and/or fog resources. One naive approach is to upload the IoT tasks to the fogs for processing based on their geographic locations [7].

Figure 1: Fog node

The Internet of Things (IoT) is one of the emerging technologies that promise to transform the way on how people work and live [8]. The term IoT refers to a network of physical objects “things” that contain embedded systems with

connectivity and computing power to exchange data with other devices and systems over the Internet [9].

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

Figure 2: Flow Chart

Steps-

- (i) Assign fog-IOT node and input parameters or model designing configuration.
- (ii) Now make a model for OFDMA and NOMA fog IOT system.
- (iii) Simulation is done using MATLAB 8.3.0.532 version.
- (iv) Now calculate sum rate with respect to power transmission.
- (v) Also calculate sum rate with respect to number of users.
- (vi) Now calculate all generated and compare results from previous work.

Figure 2 is showing flow chart of proposed work. In which after applying proposed algorithm calculate sum rate vs power and sum rate vs number of users. The optimization problem is first formulated to maximize the sum rate of the two-user NOMA system, and the solution is then generalized to the multi-user case. In order to guarantee that each user is able to achieve its target data rate, the optimization will include nonlinear constraints of proportional fairness. It is important to point out that by using the proportional fairness constraint, once the minimum rates for all users are satisfied, the remaining resources will also be allocated in a proportional

manner. Such approach is important to maintain fairness in distributing the radio resources among these users and to ensure that the weak users have enough power to decode their own data from the received signal while treating the stronger users as noise, and to ensure that the stronger users have enough power to apply SIC and cancel the effect of the weak users and detect their own data.

$$P_{RB} = P_s^{(L)} + P_s^{(H)} = \frac{P_t}{S} \tag{eq 1}$$

Without this constraint, the maximum sum rate could simply be achieved by allocating all the bandwidth and power to one user or a few users who have the best channel conditions and not all users will be allowed to transmit. In addition, another important property of this constraint is that it can utilize the potential advantage of NOMA over OMA. The minimum rate requirement is assigned to each user based on the large scale fading factor (the distance based path loss and the Log-normal shadowing factor) experienced by that user in addition to the small scale fading effects. Since path loss and shadowing is more dominant and vary slowly, the proportionality constraint is therefore effectively more long term rather than short term.

$$P_s^{(H)} = - \frac{(|h_s^{(H)}|^2 + |h_s^{(L)}|^2) B_s N_0}{2|h_s^{(H)}|^2|h_s^{(L)}|^2} + \frac{\psi_3 \sqrt{B_s N_0}}{2|h_s^{(H)}|^2|h_s^{(L)}|^2 \sqrt{\Gamma_1}} \tag{eq 2}$$

Solving the formulated problem in to requires a numerical solution or some iterative algorithm for suboptimal solution. Therefore, we first propose a low complexity sub-optimal approach that allocates the power equally among all the RBs. In other words, the total transmission power in each RB is set to be Using this assumption along with the optimization steps that are depicted in Appendix A, the sub-optimal power for the strong user is found to be

$$P_s^{(L)} = \frac{2|h_s^{(H)}|^2|h_s^{(L)}|^2 P_{RB} + (|h_s^{(H)}|^2 + |h_s^{(L)}|^2) B_s N_0}{2|h_s^{(H)}|^2|h_s^{(L)}|^2} - \frac{\psi_3 \sqrt{B_s N_0}}{2|h_s^{(H)}|^2|h_s^{(L)}|^2 \sqrt{\Gamma_1}} \tag{eq 3}$$

It is worth mentioning that the superscripts and are included just to distinguish the parameters of the users with the better channel gain from those with weaker channel gains at the selected RB and not over all RBs. It also does not necessarily mean that is higher than, where it could be less than or equal to depending on the final values from the proposed closed form solutions.

III. SIMULATION RESULT

Proposed work is simulated using MATLAB environment. Input parameter which is taken to implementation is following.

Table 1: Input Parameters

Sr. No.	Parameter	Value
1	Cell Diameter (D)	300
2	Path loss Exponent (v)	3
3	Noise Power Density (N0)	-174

4	Total Bandwidth (WT)	5
5	No. of RBs (S)	25
6	Bandwidth per RB (Bs)	200
7	No. of subcarriers per RB(Nc)	12

Figure 3: Transmission power vs sum rate
Figure 3 presenting transmission power and sum rate of existing approaches and NOMA. It is clear that NOMA gives significant better performance than previous.

Table 2: Simulation Parameter-I

Sr. No	Approach	Transmission Power	Sum Rate
1	ERPA	30	10
2	ACPA	30	18
3	OFDMA	30	25
4	Proposed NOMA	30	58

Figure 4: Number of users vs sum rate

Figure 4 presenting number of users and sum rate of existing approaches and NOMA. It is clear that NOMA gives significant better performance than previous.

Table 3: Simulation Parameter-II

Sr.	Approach	No of users	Sum Rate
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No	Approach	Sum Rate	Simulation Time
1	ERPA	28	4
2	ACPA	28	8
3	OFDMA	28	16
4	Proposed NOMA	28	19

Figure 5: Comparison of sum-rate when power is 30dBm

Figure 6: Comparison of sum-rate when user is 28

Figure 5 and 6 are showing comparison of simulated parameter of previous and proposed work. It is clear that proposed method gives significance improvement

Table 4: Result Comparison

Sr. No	Parameter	Previous work	Proposed Work
1	Technique	NOMA	Hybrid
2	Sum rate (Kbps)	27	46
3	Cov Prob.	1	1
4	Simulation Time	30 Sec	9 Sec

IV. CONCLUSION

Fog –IOT based NOMA and MIMO are technologies for improving the spectrum efficiency for 5G wireless communications. The technologies have large benefits in terms of energy efficiency, spectrum efficiency, robustness, and reliability. Current base stations are both expensive and have poor efficiency at high power levels and there are proposals to replace them with massive combined modules featuring low cost and low power consumption. Resource

allocation is a major challenge in fog IOT node communication. In this paper Resource Block was allocated using the Hybrid and NOMA algorithm of RBs allocation and classification algorithm. Due to this algorithm the power consumption gets reduced and the sum rate against the Transmission Power was increased. Two sub-optimal power allocation methods have been proposed to allocate the transmission power to each user in a two-user scenario. In addition, to optimize the sum rate for a large number of users, the proposed techniques are extended to a multi-user scenario by the vertical pairing concept. Simulation results show that NOMA provides better performance than OFDMA. In future this process will be extended to analysis of real time value with reduction of Signal to Noise Ratio with the Resource Block algorithm and Classification algorithm. Total 28 users assigned and 30db power applied. Proposed NOMA with resource block technique achieves higher sum rate than existing with number of users and applied power.

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